

A BRIEF HISTORY OF THE "SMARANDACHE FUNCTION" (III)

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ADDENDA (III) :

New References concerninig this function (got by the editorial board after August 1, 1994):

{ See the previous two issues of the journal for the first and second parts of this article }

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- "SMARANDACHE NUMBERS": $S(n)$, for $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, [M0453],
- and
- "SMARANDACHE QUOTIENTS": for each integer $n > 0$, find the smallest k such that nk is a factorial; [M1669];
- and
- "SMARANDACHE DOUBLE FACTORIALS": $F(n)$ is the smallest integer such that $F(n)!!$ is divisible by n ; [A7922] in the electronic version.